

Critiquing Black Art in Azeez Afeez Adeoti's Ceramic Portraiture

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Abstract

Black art, an emancipatory terminology against white supremacy is traceable to the crusade led by Amiri Baraka and the host of other Negroes in America. This Black social, cultural, religious, political, economic and artistic awakening started as a literary front. It later has visual presence with parallel visibility in other parts of the globe. In Africa, its manifest was evident in liberal and visual arts. Visually, it impacted Nigerian art with observable writings, drawings, paintings, sculptures, textiles, graphics, photography and ceramics of renown and budding artists. Their operations have been hyped in recent times, courtesy of the social media. However, this hype had no commensurate impact on scholarship, significantly with regards to ceramics. A gap this study attempted to fill by critiquing black art in ceramics with particular preference to Azeez Afeez Adeoti's works. Adeoti is a budding Nigerian ceramicist with buzzing social media presence, showcasing prevalent Black art portraiture renditions. Six (6) of his Black art pieces, executed between 2021 and 2025 were critiqued. This paper identified *Sgraffito* as his portraiture technique and signature, apparent on tile and vase canvases. These portraiture attest partial and full facial treatments of self, relatives and icons, expressed in realism. The critiqued pieces reflect unique Yoruba identity, civility and nationality, which are in tandem with United Nations Sustainable Development Goal's articles five (5) gender equality and ten (10) reduced inequalities. Conclusively the study hoped its finding will challenge narratives around Black art beyond social media, provoking it scholarly reawakening particularly in Nigeria and the globe in general.

Keywords: Azeez Afeez Adeoti, *Sgraffito*, ceramics, critique, realism, separatism

Introduction

Black art is synonymous to the crusade that grew out of a politically and culturally charged environment, where artists of Black descent created politically engaging works that captured African American cultural and historical experiences in America [1]. The crusaderism is called Black Arts Movement (BAM), traceable to the 1960s success story of the sit-ins and public demonstrations of Black students, who later form politicised cultural groups of humanists, intellectuals and artists [2]. Prominent among them is Amiri Baraka, publicist, essayist and poet who establish the Black Arts Repertory Theatre School (BARTS) in 1965 [3]. His poem "Black Art" though controversial but poetically profound, merging

politics with art, criticising the inadequate representations of Black struggle into a unified, pure and unapologetic black narratives, devoid of white subjugation [3].

BAM arguably produced some of the most exciting, though different art forms; consisting but not limited to poetry, drama, dance, music and visual art. It no doubt, influenced the world of literature with the portrayal of different voices of ethnic nationalities, and also spurred experimentalism. Observably, is the establishment of Black own publishing houses, magazines and journals like *Liberator*, *The Crusader*, and *Freedomways* [4, 5, 6]. They created a national community of ideology and aesthetics, where African-American artistic style and subject were displayed and debated [3]. Larry Neal, Karenga, Ishmael Reed and Amiri Baraka were some of the era's exponents of Black separatism.

According to Larry Neal, BAM is simply Black aesthetic spirituality, saying;

When we speak of a 'Black aesthetic', several things are meant. Some of which are the assumption... [of] an existential basis for aesthetics in African-American cultural tradition; the usable elements of the Third World culture; and the destruction of white things, ideas, and... world [7].

Her definitions encouraged Black separatism, facilitate hope and further strengthen black ideals, solidarity, and creativity [8]. In Karenga's view, BAM is an art that... expose the enemy, praise the people, and support the Black revolution by claiming and returning to African culture and tradition [9,10, 11]. Ishmael Reed share some of his artistic and thematic appraisals, noting thus;

... BAM inspire a whole lot of Black people to write... as a result of the multiculturalistic example of the 1960s. Blacks gave the example that you don't have to assimilate, rather you could do your own thing, get into your own background, history, tradition and culture [12].

He concluded his submission by saying; "We are preaching virtue and natural sense of the self in a world, where all men [must] live in equity" [12, 13].

Hughes advocated the need for black[s]... to resist external control of their art [14, 15, 16, 17]. A call honoured by Jeff Donaldson, Wadsworth Jarrell, William Walker, Carolyn Lawrence, Askia M. Touré and Laini Slyvia Abernathy [15, 16]. These fine artists, visually brought BAM to life in 1967 through a group called Organization of Black American Culture (OBAC). They jointly painted the *Wall of Respect*, a mural that represented BAM; what it stood for and who it was celebrating (Plate 1). The wall play host to black celebrities, among them are Elijah Muhammad, Martin Luther King Jr., Nat Turner, Malcolm X, Aretha Franklin, Gwendolyn Brooks, Muhammad Ali and Gwendolyn Brooks, W.E.B. Du Bois,

Harriet Tubman and Marcus Garvey [17, 18]. The mural was a renowned symbol of BAM in Chicago, representing black culture and creativity. Its parallel in Nigeria was evident in *Natural Synthesis*, a separatist term coined by the Zaria art school's Alpha sets (Zarian Rebels), against Eurocentrism [19].

Plate 1

1967 Wall of Respect, Chicago, Robert A. Sengstacke, Wikipedia

Both BAM and Zarian Rebels emphasised the importance of art for the Black community, promoting consciousness in terms of self worth and recognition. By 1975 over 1,500 mural installations were painted in black neighborhoods across the United States of America (USA), Chicago alone had over 200 of such paintings [20, 21]. Similarly, the Zarian Rebels, advocated indigenous ingenuity, joining forces with like minds to establish Society of Nigerian Artists (SNA) in 1963 [22, 23]. This association transformed the artistic landscape of Nigeria, fostering indigenous creations in drawing, painting, sculpture, textile, graphics, photography and ceramics [24, 25]. In the USA, ceramicist Marva Lee Pitchford-Jolly, contributed her quarter to BAM through her works "Story Pots" [26, 27]. Marva's pieces bring to mind contributions of other leading ceramic voices around the globe, significantly those from African descent.

Siddig El Nigoumi of Sudan, Magdalene Anyango Namakhiya Odundo of Kenya, Hajjah Ladi Kwali of Gwari, Nigeria and Madame Tunrayo Àyinké Ayinla of Adeta, Nigeria made the list. Their contributions were diversely unique and aptly symbolic [28]. Siddig El Nigoumi's contribution was apparent in burnished coffee-pots and other household vessels, obtained through smoke-stains of burning newspaper [29]. Dame Magdalene Odundo's impact is noticed through her black burnished finishes [30]. Hajjah Ladi Kwali was

unequivocally the most acclaimed Nigerian ceramicist with profound prowess in black art through her burnished wares [30, 31]. While, Madame Túnráyò Àyìnké Àyìnlá, is recently recognised for her contribution to wares black burnishing [28, 32, 33].

These ceramicists no doubt, resonate with Black identity and ideology [30, 33]. Their works can be classified as Neo traditional, offering array of illuminating perspectives and its enduring relevance in contemporary discourse [34]. Ceramic art offers artists myriad creative possibilities, allowing them to explore form, texture, colour, symbol and style [35, 36, 37]. As an art medium, it includes a wide variety of works, from functional utensils to sculptural pieces [38]. Functionality of ceramic articles were adjudged expressive of artistic ingenuity, prevalent in residential and commercial architecture [39, 40]. Their shapes, forms, textures, and surface treatments interact to create a rich tapestry of artistic discoveries and expressions [41]. Rhodes [42] said every piece of art that the artists create provides a window into their values, beliefs, and aesthetic tastes. It directly or indirectly reflects the artist's experience, offering insights into individual personality.

As such, gaining insight into ceramic artist's contributions is however, necessary in appreciating the manner at which medium is changing and redefining its artistry [43, 44]. Ceramic artistry is an interplay of tradition, culture, modernity and creative expression, where each piece speaks about the artistic journey and the intimate connection between the material and the maker [45]. However, many of the nascent Nigerian ceramic art sensations have reduced their artistry to the social media, with little to nothing literarily. Among such ceramicists is Adeoti Azeez Afeez (Plate 2), with social media presence, culminating at the moment approximately two thousand and three hundred (2,300) followers on Instagram alone [46]. His literary visibility is next to nothing, considering the dearth of scholarship on his prolificity, despite contributing to Nigeria's ceramic art and in particular, Black art. As such, this study attempted critiquing his background, practice and Black art with particular regards to portraiture.

Azeez was born in 1988 to the family of Mr. and Mrs. Adeoti, who hail from *Isehin* in Oyo State, Nigeria. As the firstborn child of his parents, he learn early to prioritised excellence, been his mother's anthem; chorused to his ears, growing up. He recalled two of his Mum rhymes, the first goes thus;

Omo to ba sipa
N'iya re n po

The child that raises arm
Is the one his mother backed

The second was;

*Omo to ba jafafa,
Ni ti baba e.
Eyi to ba jafara,
Ni t'iya e.*

The child that is proficiently smart,
Is his father's own.
The one that is ridiculously slow,
Is his mother's own.

The above rhymes he said, helped largely in shaping and reshaping his life orientation towards pursuing excellence [47]. A virtue, he held at heart during and after his formal education. Azeez early education was completed at ECOWAS Group of Schools and Vetland Grammar School, Lagos State, Nigeria. He from there proceeded to the School of Art, Design, and Printing Technology, Yaba College of Technology (Yabatech), at a tender age of fourteen (14) years old in pursuance of higher education.

Plate 2

Azeez Afeez Adeoti calm pose at his home studio, Luwoye, 2024

He respectively bagged his Ordinary National Diploma (OND) and Higher National Diploma (HND) at age of sixteen (16) and nineteen (19) years olds. Adeoti's exceptional talent was recognized with an award for Best Graduating Student in Industrial Design in 2017 majoring in ceramics. His tertiary education at Yabatech provided him with a solid foundation in painting and sculpture, which were seamlessly integrated into his ceramic practice. Adeoti's love for clay, its artistic versatility, expressivity and possibility led him to specialise in ceramics [47]. This possibility is reflected in his current works, achieved through Sgraffito drawings blended with traditional and contemporary motifs. Azeez is a Lagos-base startup ceramist who acknowledged the leadership influences of Ato Arinze and Natalie Kassie Djakou, recognising the duo as his mentors [47].

Adeoti has a buzzing social media presence and several art exhibitions both locally and internationally to his credit. His social media handles included Facebook, Instagram, X, Thread, and Linked In. *Open House* organized by the Department of Fine Art, Yaba College

of Technology in 2016; *Convergence*, Ministry of Arts and Culture, Ibadan in 2019; *Beyond Borders*, Lagos in 2020; *Life in My City*, Enugu in 2022; *Stay Black and Die*”, Portland, USA in 2022; *Reserved Safari*, Moscow in 2023; *(Sur)face Exhibition Part II*, London in 2023; and *Future fair*, United States in 2024 were some of the group exhibitions he had featured [47]. Adeoti’s 2025 solo exhibition in Lagos was his first. Apart from his *Agbarha-Otor* workshop experiences, Adeoti recently won himself a two (2) months residency at the Jingdenzhen University in China [49].

A significant influence on his work is Yoruba film and Black identity. He believed in the importance of appreciating African roots amidst modernity. Adeoti’s works often x-ray the abandonment of indigenous cultures in favour of Western ideals, urging a balance between modernity and cultural preservation. His creative process involved a dynamic interplay of idea development and execution. He starts by sketching his ideas, but these often evolve as he works allowing new inspiration to emerge. This adaptability is a crucial aspect of his practice, enabling him to refine and enhance his work continuously. Adeoti’s art is deeply personal, drawing on his Yoruba heritage as an *Oloje* (Possessor of Masquerade). He has succeeded in exploring and reflecting his masquerade’s philosophy and philology in terms of fabric colouration, patterning and motifs [47].

Adeoti’s artistic motifs and compositional influences also included inspirations from ancient traditions of northern, eastern and southern Nigeria. His background in painting also helped in adding brilliance and depth to his pieces, using derived engobes from oxides to achieve different colours. *Eniafelamo*, *Introspection*, *Profile of my mother*, *Ori Inu I*, *Moremi Ajasoro*, and *Ki Ade o pe lori I* are the selected portraiture rendered between 2021 and 2025. They are consequently critiqued as thus (Plates 3-8);

Plate 3

Eniafelamo, 2021, 32 x 32 x .5 cm, Instagram

This piece is rendered on four fired tiles, each gives an impression of zoomed photographic snapshot with different facial expressions suggestive of introversible and extroversible state of mind. The first shot play host to a face featuring only the right side eye and nose. The second shot, showcased a conservative face with smiling lips, nose and teeth, the third shot housed an exited face with glimpse of the eyes, nose and laughter, revealing majorly the upper part of the teethes. The forth shot housed a face with the left nose and an eye. These four slides and their facial intents or contexts can be likened to a real world situation where appearance can be deceptive. Little wonder why Adeoti titled this piece *Eniafelamo*, a Yoruba phrasal maxim [50], meaning “Those we love, we know”, with a rider, *A o mo eni to feni* (We do not know those that love one). The piece like its title brings to mind the rarity of love as evident in today's perverse world where there is no permanent friend but interest. The piece corroborates the fact that loving someone is not a guarantee, the person is loved in return. The gestures in the snapshot can be surmised as involuntary or voluntary expression of happiness, pleasure, amusement, goodwill and anxiety towards someone or thing.

Plate 4

Introspection, 2022, 42 x 58.5 x .5 cm, Instagram

Introspection is the title of this piece, produced in 2022. Its fore ground play host to an image of a male in his late teens or early twenties and a background of rectilinear and curvilinear motifs. The piece was rendered on square tiles, totaling twelve (12) in number. Ten (10) of tiles were derived from fired clay, complimented with two mirror sheets, These two mirror sheets draws attention of attendant audience to the central figure, adorn in light

and dark strip shirt with white collar. The face of the central figure was concealed with one of the square mirror, giving the puzzle impression; which creates retrospective and introspective illusion of one's true identity. The prevailing rectilinear and curvilinear features of the piece are commonly seen in textile designs and are suggestive of conjugal intersection, procreation and semblance. The contrasting patterns and colors within each tile suggests the multifaceted nature of human experiences. However, the mirror (*Jigi* or *Diji*) [51] alluded to Yoruba metaphors of masculinity and offspring, observable in the sayings below;

... <i>Baba ni jigi</i>	...Father is mirror
And;	
... <i>Omo eni, ni jigi eni,</i>	...Ones child is ones mirror
<i>Ko gbodo fo o, jigi x2</i>	It must not be broken, mirror x2

The take from the above sayings is the masculine cum offspring personification of mirror, its role in family or nation building, which must not be allowed to erode. The mirror consequently attests perfect or imperfect retrospection and introspection in attendant audiences.

Plate 5

Profile of My Mother, 2022, 45 x 32.5 x 15 cm, Facebook

This piece titled “*Profile of my mother*” was executed in 2022 on an inverted conical vase, measuring 45 x 32.5 x 15 cm. The vase was achieved by hand built technique. It played host to a dominant female figure, supposedly in her late fifties (50s) or early sixties (60s). This dominant cum central figure is visually adorned in a white patterned blouse, complimented with all back *Suku* hairdo [52], circular earring and a focused gaze facing the east. The figure, though that of Adeoti's mother, it represents womanhood and all she stand for. Little wonder why Adeoti's rendition of this vase and its bold horizontal and vertical

lines are suggestive of the globe and its equator where the central female figure represent the map of Africa. Her eastward gaze, an attestation to articulate agility of an individual aiming for gold through vigour and openness to the vicissitude of life. Her white patterned blouse further attests, purity, fruitfulness and growth, evident in the blossoming flora (hibiscus) motifs [53]. Through, this work Adeoti pay homage to his mother, considering her contributions to the man he has become in terms of love, care, support and encouragements.

Plate 6

Ori Inu I (Inner self series), 2023, 53 x 43 x .5 cm. Luwoye, 2024

This piece titled “*Ori Inu I*” was rendered in 2023 on a rectangular fired clay tile, measuring 53 x 43 x .5 cm. It is Adeoti’s first in its series, capturing Yoruba concept of man’s inner or metaphysical essence and segmented into two of fore and back grounds. The foreground is a high relief, housing six intersecting concentric circles, complimented with four trapezoidal arch projectiles like that of *Arewa* wall architecture motif. Each of the six concentric circles were delineated by six curvilinear lines, solidly adding depth and visual framing to the piece background. This background comprised two tiny pillars, two arch beam and a central figure. The central figure, a male bust is of utmost interest here, considering it engobe silhouette rendition, focused gaze and surface line delineation, a reminiscence of stylised crucifix emblazon. The emblazon can be likened to infrared radiation, suggestive of metaphysical mask which needed to be placated like the title *Ori Inu* (inner head or essence) that must not damage the outer essence (*Ko ma ba tode je*) [54]. Adeoti’s adoption of architectural structure and human figure and the application of white, gold and black hues on

this piece signifies haven, enlightenment, peace, elegance and imperfection, which are paramount virtue of a metaphysical essence. However, the westward posture of the central male figure signifies vitality, longevity and wisdom [55].

Plate 7

Moremi Ajasoro, 2025, 53cm x 70.5cm x .5cm, Instagram

This piece titled “Moremi Ajasoro” was produced in memory and celebration of power, strength, legacy and creativity of a Yoruba woman. Its picture plane featured a charming damsel in its foreground and diverse motifs on its background, made from fired tiles; totaling twelve (12) sheets. This damsel faced her potential audience directly in a charming but unassuming manner. She was adorned in one on one braids, similar to *Moremi* plaiting style [52] (Adeoye, 2010: 172). Her gaze, reminiscent of King Sunny Ade’s position on facial gesture in his lyrical line, noting thus;

*...Oju ti eri en,
Sime sime, sime sime.
Ina le ri en, x2
Palaba ole se yin lese* [56].

...This face (eye) you are seeing,
Unassuming, unassuming.
Fire is what you are seeing, x2
Broadly large and it can be injurious.

The above line is largely in consonance with Adeoti’s central figure, whose modest and unostentatious simplicity is nothing but a steaming hot fire. Little wonder why history has it that, this Ife matriarch use her physical and meta-physical charm to seduce her Igbo captors and in return lay hold of their secret [57]. She consequently, liberate and emancipate her people from the Igbo’s mental slavery and hostage. The realistic rendering of the piece and her frontal gaze attests now or now capturing attention of her prospective audience into

fantasising beauty, charm and history. Its complimenting background motifs attest fire, pathway, liberty and unison.

Plate 8

Ki Ade pe lori I, 2025, 89 cm Diameter, Facebook

Ki Ade pe lori I is first in its series, executed in 2025. It is a self portraiture capturing Adeoti adorning himself a conical crown. The piece was a product of his escapade to *Isehin*, rendered on a circular board, measuring 89 cm in diameter. This circular shape is supposedly simulated from somewhat Yoruba divination board (*Opon Ifa*) [58]. The board was divided into eight parts. He was adorned in orange velvet *Dansiki* with gold embroidered round neck, two linearly placed star knot motifs and four star knot motifs on each side of the pocket [59]. The crown Adeoti wore in this piece is synonymous to *Ade Are*, very much like that of *Oni of Ife*, the cradle of Yoruba race [60]. It is a beaded conical crown, typically adorned during coronation of a ranking king has link to the source in Yoruba land. The crown is visually embellished with a total of seven birds, human faces and inverted triangles that form diamond shapes round it. One of the birds is seen balanced at the topmost edge of the crown, while the rest six were suspended round the crown's slope in ascending order. The birds and the faces signify the presence of celestial (the witches and the ancestors) bodies keeping watch. Also evident on the edge of the board are incised line motifs of four rosaries, sixteen faces, two elongated knobs, sixteen cola nuts and two bows and arrows, signifying divination, corpus, placation and protection respectively. Their signification is in consonance with Adeoti's title "*Ki Ade pe lori*", meaning may the crown stay long on the head.

Conclusion

Adeoti Azeez Afeez, though a prolific ceramicist, yet literarily underrepresented in contemporary Nigerian art, despite his contributions to contemporary discourse on Black art ceramics. This study provides a comprehensive critique of Black art, recognising the efforts of its path finding crusaders and their contributions to the emancipatory call for freedom from white supremacy and Western subjugation. These crusaders at multiple counts responded to prevailing artistic realities of their time, observably through writings, drawings, paintings, sculptures, textiles, graphics, photography and ceramics [61]. Examining Adeoti's background, practice, and selected portraiture produced between 2021 and 2025, the research highlights how he seamlessly integrates his foundation in painting and sculpture into ceramic artistry.

He masterfully manipulates clay to explore multifaceted dimensions of form, texture, and color, using slab methods, engobe painting, and intricate Sgraffito techniques, apparent on square, rectangular, circular and conical tiles and vases respectively. Adeoti believes in openness, consistency, determination, authenticity and visibility as a key to gaining recognition in the art world. He stresses the importance of attending exhibitions, connecting with others in the field, and seeking help when needed. His journey underscores the value of persistence and continuous learning rooted in Yoruba heritage. Much like the foundational ethos of the Black Arts Movement (BAM) and the Zairian art Rebels, Adeoti resists external cultural hegemony, using his art to promote self-worth, community consciousness, and African identity. A view that is exemplified in *Eniafelamo*, *Introspection*, *Ori Inu I*, *Moremi Ajasoro*, and *Ki Ade pe lori I*, which critique westernization while celebrating indigenous philosophy.

Corroborating the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal's articles five (5) gender equality and ten (10) reduced inequalities. His ability to balance a vibrant social media presence with global exhibitions demonstrates the shifting paradigm of contemporary art visibility. Ultimately, this research addresses a critical gap in academic scholarship regarding nascent Nigerian artists. It stands as a valuable reference material for researchers, instructors, and upcoming ceramicists, ensuring that Adeoti's profound contributions to indigenous ingenuity and the broader tapestry of global Black identity are preserved and appreciated.

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Conflict of Interest

None

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